

RISK FACTORS, DIAGNOSIS AND POSSIBILITIES OF CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF GENITAL PROLAPSE

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Abstract

This article presents a review of the current literature concerning the problem of pelvic organ prolapse in women. It lists the risk factors for this pathology, the possibilities of diagnosing this condition, as well as options for conservative correction of genital prolapse. The authors also present their own experience of treatment of pelvic organ prolapse using silicone gynaecological pessaries manufactured by CJSC "Medical enterprise Simurg".

Conclusion. 1. The use of vaginal pessaries is a safe and effective alternative to surgical methods of treatment of pelvic organ prolapse, especially when surgical intervention is impossible. 2. The use of silicone gynaecological pessaries was accompanied by satisfaction with treatment after three months of follow-up in at least 85% of patients, as well as improved quality of life in 88% of women.

Keywords: genital prolapse, pessaries, conservative treatment

Internal genital prolapse is a pathological change in the position of the uterus and/or vaginal walls, clinically manifested by the displacement of the genital organs to the border of the vaginal vestibulum or beyond. The presence of genital prolapse entails changes in the function of adjacent organs, manifested by urinary incontinence, anal sphincter failure, constipation, etc. [1, 2]. This condition is not life-threatening, but it can significantly reduce a woman's quality of life [3, 4]. There are a number of clinical diagnoses that characterise to a greater or lesser extent the severity and severity of internal genital prolapse and prolapse: prolapse, cystocele, rectocele, incomplete and complete prolapse of the uterus and vaginal walls [5, 6, 7].

Among gynaecological pathologies, genital prolapse accounts for 30%, while surgical interventions for this problem are performed in no more than 15% of gynaecological patients [8]. The most vulnerable group is women aged 60-69 years, the incidence of this pathology progressively increases with increasing age. Recurrence of prolapse is common, requiring repeated surgical intervention or the use of non-surgical techniques. It is not possible to determine the actual incidence of genital prolapse, but it is generally believed that at least 40% of women aged 49-79 years suffer from this pathology [9], and cystocele is the most frequently detected in them - at least 31% of the total number of patients with prolapse [10].

The classic *risk factor* for the development of genital prolapse is considered to be excessive physical activity accompanied by increased intra-abdominal pressure, which leads to mechanical displacement of the uterine body together with the vaginal walls beyond their physiological location [11, 12]. Not only lifting of heavy objects and power sports, but also chronic pathology of the gastrointestinal and respiratory tracts

play a role. The latter lead to chronic constipation and chronic cough, which causes episodic acute increase in intra-abdominal pressure and excessive stretching of musculofascial structures that provide normal topography of internal genital organs within the small pelvis [13, 14]. Pregnancy and natural childbirth, especially multiple deliveries with a large foetus, are also important risk factors [15, 16].

It has also been noted that the incidence of genital prolapse in Caucasian women is 2.5-3 times higher than in non-European women [17]. Additional studies are required to clarify this fact, but hypotheses are already being put forward about the importance of the characteristics of the pelvic ligaments and fascia in Asian and African women as a protective factor against genital prolapse [18].

One of the most recent and convincing theories for the onset and progression of genital prolapse is connective tissue failure, including undifferentiated connective tissue disease (UCD) [19]. This theory is supported by the fact that genital prolapse is quite common in women who have not given birth, as well as in patients who do not suffer from constipation/cough, and who are not involved in sports and physical labour [20, 21]. Genital prolapse is also characteristically combined with other manifestations of UCD - hernias of various localisations, myopia, heart defects and others.

The state of hypoestrogenism during menopause causes a high incidence of genital prolapse at the age of over 49 years [22, 23]. Genetic predisposition may play an important role as a risk factor for internal genitalia prolapse in women who have not given birth [24].

Depending on the dysfunction of a particular pelvic floor component, the following types of prolapse are distinguished: anterior prolapse (cystocele, urethrocele and cystourethrocele), middle prolapse (uterine

prolapse and vaginal vault prolapse) and posterior pelvic floor prolapse (rectocele and enterocele). The POP-Q system proposed by the International Continence Society (ICS) is currently considered to be the most used and reproducible classification of genital prolapse. According to this classification, 9 parameters measured in the sagittal plane are to be evaluated. The most distal part of the vaginal wall is used to determine the stage of the process. According to the POP-Q system, it is possible to keep a unified register of data of patients with genital prolapse, as well as to monitor the dynamics of the process and the effectiveness of treatment. The advantages of this classification are also high reproducibility of the results, lack of dependence on the patient's position, and accurate quantification of anatomical landmarks [25, 26].

Formation of genital prolapse takes years. At the same time, the dysfunction of the genital organs often recedes into the background after disorders of the urinary system and rectal function. Nevertheless, the main symptom of prolapse is the feeling of a foreign object at the vestibulum of the vagina [27]. The prolapse of the uterine body and/or vaginal walls is followed by maceration, fissures and ulceration of the mucous membranes covering the prolapsing organs. Accession of secondary infection is often takes place in the focus of damage to the mucous membranes. As prolapse progresses, the patient notes increasing pain in the lower abdomen, back pain, swelling and cyanosis [28]. Sexual dysfunction is also important, manifested by decreased vaginal sensitivity and dyspareunia. In general, there is a positive correlation between the degree of genital prolapse symptoms and its severity, i.e. asymptomatic patients tend to have a lower severity [29, 30].

The examination of patients with genital prolapse traditionally begins with the collection of medical history, as well as the clarification of risk factors. In the management of these patients, the impact of the disease on their quality of life must be taken into account. For this purpose, a number of validated questionnaires are used: Pelvic Floor Distress Inventory, Pelvic Floor Impact Questionnaire-7 (PFIQ-7), Pelvic Organ Prolapse and Incontinence Sexual Function Questionnaire (PISQ) and some others. Each has both advantages and disadvantages of use, but in general allow a full assessment of the impact of genital prolapse on different aspects of patients' lives.

General examination is primarily aimed at detecting signs of undifferentiated connective tissue disease since the degree of severity of this condition will largely determine the treatment and prognosis of the disease in question. The main signs of UCD are joint hypermobility, skin hyperelastosis, varicose veins, flat feet, scoliosis and myopia [31, 32]. Examination in the gynaecological chair should include assessment of the shape and location of the urethra; the condition of the vaginal mucosa, the presence of scars and pathological discharge; the degree of vaginal wall prolapse; the localisation of the uterine body and cervix, as well as their mobility; and the status of the tendon centre of the perineum. Functional tests are also performed at this time: coughing and pushing test (Valsalva) without repositioning

the prolapse, in order to qualitatively characterise urinary and/or faecal incontinence. These tests are then performed with repositioning of the prolapsing organs using a gynaecological mirror/manually with the bladder filled. It is also important to determine the strength of contraction of the pelvic floor muscles, assess the diameter of the vaginal entrance and the height of the perineum. In some cases, additional methods of examination may be required, including a comprehensive urodynamic study, ultrasound, and MRI [33, 34].

The **treatment** of genital prolapse is sometimes extremely challenging. To choose between conservative or surgical treatment, the following aspects should be taken into account: the severity of the process; the condition and age of the patient; the interest in preserving sexual and/or reproductive function; the possibility of a complete surgical treatment; the concomitant pathology, including somatic pathology; and the patient's consent to the proposed treatment.

Conservative treatment at the first stage includes lifestyle modification. The patient should reduce physical activity leading to an increase in intra-abdominal pressure (limit weight lifting, eliminate constipation, stop smoking). It should be noted that to date, convincing data from multicentre prospective studies concerning the impact of the above modification have not been obtained, and there are only data from noninvasive (observational) studies on the significance of obesity of constipation for the formation of genital prolapse [35, 36, 37].

The effectiveness of pelvic floor augmentation exercises (Kegel exercises) has been demonstrated for the prevention and treatment of urinary incontinence [38, 39]. Data from randomised controlled trials have shown significant reductions in symptom severity and POP-Q scores [40]. A Cochrane systematic review also reported some positive effects of this exercise on genital prolapse symptom severity [41]. However, the traditional method of performing Kegel exercises is not always clear to patients, as well as the essence of performing some steps, and requires serious concentration and motivation. At present, special vaginal cones (trade mark ColpoTrain™) are available on the Belarussian market, which act as weights and eliminate the need to perform complex algorithms of tension/relaxation of the pelvic floor muscles. The patient only needs to insert a cone of suitable weight into the vagina and try to hold it in place for a set period of time. The cones are hypoallergenic and resistant to long-term use.

The use of pessaries is recommended for severe symptomatic genital prolapse. This treatment is widely used abroad as a first-line treatment for a number of prolapse-related conditions [42]. The indications for treatment with pessaries are the presence of symptomatic prolapse, impossibility (refusal) of surgical treatment at this stage, recurrent prolapse, severe concomitant somatic pathology. There are several main types of pessaries: supportive (ring-shaped, cup-shaped) and volume-forming (cubic, "doughnut-shaped"). The choice of a particular type of pessary depends largely on the degree of prolapse. Thus, for the 1st and 2nd degrees the most suitable are ring-shaped modifications,

with the help of which the correction of existing disorders in most cases is successful. Ring-shaped pessaries can be used as an initiating conservative therapy and for grade 3 and 4 prolapse as a test therapy (temporary option). The possible presence of cystocele and rectocele should also be taken into account, in which case the insertion of a mushroom-shaped ring or cup-shaped perforated pessary is indicated. To select the size of the pessary, the width of the vaginal entrance and the depth of the vagina must be taken into account. There are several methods for this purpose, but none of them gives an objective assessment of the parameters sought, so that the selection of the right size of pessary may be time-consuming and ineffective. The criteria for effective insertion and wearing of the pessary are: no discomfort in the orthostatic position, no discomfort during activity (coughing, walking, sneezing, pushing/defecation); insertion and removal of the pessary from the vagina are easy; the pessary does not cause urinary or defecation disorders; the pessary does not provoke new symptoms. Predictors of ineffective pessary insertion may include: short vagina (less than 6 cm); wide vaginal entrance (more than 4 transverse fingers); distal posterior vaginal prolapse (rectocele); previous surgical intervention for genital prolapse; existing or new stress urinary incontinence. As a rule, all these difficulties can be overcome by the correct selection of a pessary of the right size and/or shape.

The efficacy of this therapy has been reported in a number of non-invasive and several randomised controlled trials [43]. Thus, according to the latter, improvement in the quality of life in patients with genital prolapse with the use of pessaries was noted in 60% of cases [44]. A recent observational study by Miceli et al. showed a similar rate of successful prolapse correction with uterine ring pessaries and surgical treatment - 84.4% and 89.6%, respectively [46]. There are currently no clear unified algorithms for the selection and use of vaginal pessaries. There are no national/international guidelines regarding the use of devices for conservative treatment of genital prolapse. This is largely the reason why clinicians do not have a clear understanding of the mechanism of action of pessaries, and there is often confusion in determining the required form factor and size of the device. The main reasons for refusal of further conservative treatment of genital prolapse using a pessary were: discomfort of the patient when wearing the device and difficulties in reinsertion of the pessary by the patient herself after sanitation due to the lack of a convenient "syringe-injector"; failure to control the main symptoms or their progression (urinary incontinence, lack of vaginal wall retention, severe pain, profuse vaginal discharge, including suppuration); complications of the therapy (colpitis, sores, fistulas, ulcers, pessary ingrowth); revision of the patient's management in favour of surgical treatment. Contraindications to the use of pessaries are: the patient's inability to follow the rules of pessary use; the presence of vaginal fistulas, vaginal erosion, inflammatory processes of the genitals and bleeding from the vagina. An important aspect of the use of uterine pessaries is the possibility of continuing sexual life, as the

device can be removed and reinserted by the patient herself. The frequency of follow-up visits is also very controversial and varies widely country to country. Thus, the common practice in the USA is a visit every three months, while in Europe 6-month follow-up intervals are more accepted, the adequacy of which is also indicated by the results of a randomised study devoted to this issue [47]. However, it is undeniable that if the patient can be monitored regularly, if there are no significant side effects of pessary use, and if there is no progression of prolapse that makes further correction with a pessary impossible, wearing these devices can last for years.

As an addition, it is rational to use topical forms of estrogens, which are able to control the symptoms of local hypoestrogenemia and improve the long-term results of conservative and surgical therapy, while the use of estrogens does not affect the frequency and severity of side effects of uterine pessaries [45].

Currently, there are few national recommendations regarding the use of different types of pessaries, indications for insertion, replacement, and the frequency of patient follow-up. In the following, we present the experience of using different types of pessaries manufactured by CJSC "Medical enterprise Simurg" (Republic of Belarus, registration certificate No. IM-7.101558) in 156 patients of the gynaecological department of the Vitebsk Regional Clinical Specialised Centre.

The age of the patients ranged from 41 to 87 (57±3.2) years. Stage 2 prolapse occurred in 79 (50.6%) patients, stage 3 and 4 in 40 (25.6%) and 37 (23.8%) patients, respectively.

At the first stage, indications and contraindications for non-surgical correction of genital prolapse were evaluated. In our institution, such treatment is performed in the following patients:

- ✓ with the presence of symptomatic prolapse;
- ✓ with contraindications for surgical treatment of prolapse or if the patient refuses surgical treatment;
- ✓ recurrence of prolapse after surgical treatment.

Contraindications to the use of pessaries are as follows:

- χ inability to follow the rules of pessary wearing by the patient (e.g. due to neuropsychiatric disorders, including age-related disorders);
- χ vaginal fistula;
- χ Inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs;
- χ vaginal bleeding of unclear etiology;
- χ vaginal erosions, large decubital ulcers of the cervix.

In the latter case, it is possible to carry out comprehensive sanitation, including inpatient treatment.

Conservative treatment of genital prolapse in hospital settings involves the selection and insertion of a pessary. There are several main types of pessaries: supportive (ring-shaped, bowl-shaped, Figure 1a,b), volume-forming (cubic, fungiform, Donut, Gellhorn, Figure 1c, d) and universal (universal silicone gynecological pessary Dr. Zhuravlev®, Figure 1e, f).

Figure 1: Types of gynecological pessaries (manufacturer - CJSC "Medical enterprise Simurg", Republic of Belarus): a) ring-shaped, b) bowl-shaped, c) cubic, d) fungiform, e,f) universal silicone gynecological pessary Dr. Zhuravlev®

The choice of a particular type of pessary depends on the stage of prolapse (according to the POP-Q classification), as well as on the total vaginal length (TVL) and the GH distance. Thus, for stages 1 and 2, ring-shaped modifications of pessaries are most commonly used. According to our observations, the outer diameter of ring-shaped models should be 1.5cm greater than GH (pessary diameter = GH + 1.5cm), but not more than TVL - 3cm (pessary diameter \leq TVL - 3.0cm). Ring-shaped pessaries can be used for

initiating conservative therapy for stage 3, 4 prolapse as a test therapy. However, according to our observations, the percentage of expulsions of ring-shaped pessaries is high at these stages (more than 50%); therefore, the use of volume-filling and universal pessaries is more appropriate. It should be accounted that these pessary models require removal at night. This limits their use in elderly patients. The principle scheme of conservative management of patients with pelvic organ prolapse is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Scheme of conservative management of patients with pelvic organ prolapse

As a rule, patients are admitted with the results of laboratory and clinical tests, including total blood count and urine test, biochemistry, flora and oncocytoplogical smears from the cervical canal and ectocervix, therapist's report, ECG with obligatory decoding.

Then a collegial examination is carried out with the involvement of staff of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology and, if necessary, doctors of related specialities (urologist, proctologist). The examination includes a detailed collection of medical history, with clarification of it, potential and existing risk factors, as well as the impact of pathology on the quality of life of the woman. According to our data, the most frequent complaints were discomfort in the area of external genitalia, urinary and/or defecation disorders.

The examination on the gynaecological chair is performed according to the general rules. To visualise genital prolapse, Simpson spoon-shaped mirrors are used, inserted alternately into the vaginal vaults. Attention is paid to the shape and localisation of the urethral orifice, the condition of its mucosa, the presence of organic pathology (polyps, destruction); the condition of the vaginal mucosa (scars, deformation, discharge); the degree of vaginal wall prolapse at rest and under tension; the condition of the cervix (shape, localisation, location of the vaginal vaults); the shape and mobility of

the uterine body; the status of the pelvic floor muscles and its defects. Patients are also offered to perform a cough test with a filled (at least 300 ml) bladder. This test is repeated during manual or instrumental repair of the prolapse. The final stage of the special examination is the assessment of the strength and efficiency of contractions of the pelvic floor muscles, as well as rectal examination to clarify the status of the sphincters of the rectum.

After insertion of the type of pessary, determined according to the above described scheme, the woman usually stays in hospital for 24 hours for an early assessment of the effectiveness of the treatment. The criteria for the effectiveness of the insertion and wearing of the pessary are:

- ✓ the inserted pessary does not cause discomfort in the orthostatic position of the patient, during activity (coughing, walking, sneezing, pushing/defecation);
- ✓ insertion and removal of the pessary from the vagina is easy;
- ✓ the pessary does not cause urinary or defecation disorders;
- ✓ the pessary does not provoke new symptoms.

At discharge, the patient is given detailed recommendations for outpatient treatment. These include: restriction of heavy objects lifting, prophylactic vaginal

sanitation 6 days a month with vaginal suppositories containing antiseptic and antimycotic topical suppositories. If a cubic pessary or Gellhorn pessary is used, it is recommended to remove it at night. If a ring, cup or universal pessary is used, daily removal is usually not required.

The next visit to monitor the effect of the conservative treatment of genital prolapse is scheduled three weeks after discharge from hospital. During the visit, the patient is questioned about satisfaction with the treatment, the degree of manifestation of previous or new symptoms is assessed. If it is necessary to insert a pessary of a different size or type, colposcopy is performed and contraindications for the use of a pessary are excluded. Further, on an outpatient basis or after short-term hospitalisation (as a rule, this is required for elderly patients, due to the impossibility of adequate sanitation of the vagina and selection of the necessary size/type of pessary in outpatient conditions).

The second and third visits are carried out after 4 and 8 weeks from the previous visit, respectively. The programme is the same as the previous visit (interview, examination, colposcopy, assessment of vaginal microflora).

Regardless of the type of pessary used, stool regulation with oral lactulose solution is recommended. In addition, to prevent recurrences and maceration of the mucous membranes of the prolapsing walls of the vagina and cervix, local application of anti-inflammatory and antibacterial ointments is recommended, and in case of severe manifestations of estrogen deficiency, estrogen-containing vaginal suppositories are also recommended.

The main reasons for refusal of further conservative treatment of genital prolapse using a pessary were:

χ discomfort of the patient when wearing the device,

χ lack of relief of the main symptoms or their progression (urinary incontinence, lack of vaginal wall retention, severe pain syndrome, profuse vaginal discharge, including purulent discharge);

χ complications of the current therapy, as well as revision of the patient's management in favour of surgical treatment.

Our experience with the use of vaginal pessaries for the correction of pelvic organ prolapse shows that the therapy is well tolerated by the patients (satisfaction with the treatment after three months of follow-up is at least 85%), and 88% of patients reported an improvement in their quality of life.

Conclusion:

1. The use of vaginal pessaries is a safe and effective alternative to surgical treatment of pelvic organ prolapse, especially when surgical intervention is not possible.

2. The use of silicone gynaecological pessaries was accompanied by satisfaction with treatment after three months of follow-up in at least 85% of patients, as well as improved quality of life in 88% of women.

3. The use of pessaries requires a certain theoretical and practical training of the doctor.

4. Individualised tactics for the selection of the type and size of the vaginal pessary, as well as long-

term management of the patient with monthly evaluation of the effectiveness of therapy demonstrate high patient compliance rates and good clinical results.

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